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NURSING ASSISTANCE FOR PATIENTS WITH DIABETES

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МЕДСЕСТРИНСЬКА ДОПОМОГА ХВОРИМ З ЦУКРОВИМ ДІАБЕТОМ

Abstract.

The article discusses the role of a nurse in diagnosing diabetes, identifying risk factors, teaching self-control, and preventing complications.

The basis for achieving therapeutic goals is the education of patients with diabetes, the purpose of which is not only to inform them about the complications and treatment of diabetes, but also to support independent decision-making by the patients themselves through the interpretation of their own behavior and providing them with psychological help in controlling the disease. This will allow for the safe achievement of treatment goals agreed with the therapeutic team, where the nurse plays an important role as a full participant.

Анотація.

У статті розглянуто роль медичної сестри у діагностиці цукрового діабету, виявленні чинників ризику, забезпеченні навчання самоконтролю, попередженні розвитку ускладнень. Основою для досягнення терапевтичних цілей є навчання хворих з цукровим діабетом, мета якого полягає не лише в їх інформуванні про ускладнення та лікування діабету, але й у підтримці самостійного прийняття рішень самим хворим через інтерпретацію власної поведінки та надання їм психологічної допомоги в контролі над захворюванням. Це дозволить безпечно досягти узгоджених із терапевтичною командою цілей лікування, де медична сестра відіграє важливу роль як повноцінний учасник.

Key words: *diabetes, nurse, nursing care, education, treatment.*

Ключові слова: *цукровий діабет, медична сестра, медсестринська допомога, навчання, лікування.*

Introduction. Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) affect people from all walks of life and in all parts of the world. The epidemic of NCDs creates devastating consequences for the health of individuals, families and communities. Prevention and fight against these diseases is the main development imperative for the 21st century. NCDs continue to cause the greatest burden of disease worldwide. The World Health Organization (WHO) recognizes diabetes mellitus (DM) as one of the 4 major NCDs. Due to the prevalence of diabetes and its increasing incidence, it is considered a lifestyle disease. This is an important social problem, since from the moment of diagnosis, the treatment of diabetes lasts a lifetime [4].

The main part. As the burden of diabetes continues to increase worldwide, the role of nurses in diabetes care is becoming increasingly important. Recognizing their leadership position, the World Health Organization and the International Diabetes Federation have emphasized the critical role of nurses in supporting the health care system, particularly diabetes care [2]. Nurses play a key role in: providing self-control training and psychological support to help prevent complications; overcoming diabetes risk factors to prevent the disease [3].

In their research, scientists emphasize that due to the significant workload on family doctors and their limited ability to provide a full range of preventive services, it is important to involve the average medical staff. A nurse who is knowledgeable about the patient's environment and the risk factors for developing DM, such as obesity, physical inactivity, stress, heredity, and bad habits, plays a key role in prevention. It not only popularizes a healthy lifestyle, but also teaches patients to make decisions to improve their health, predict risks and avoid negative consequences [4, 5].

Health care systems in various countries are increasingly implementing nurse-led models, which are considered more patient-centered, as opposed to traditional physician-led models that emphasize drug treatment. Giving nurses more autonomy in diabetes care has been suggested as a possible way to improve patient outcomes. Comparing a nurse-led model with a traditional approach, studies have shown that the former was more effective in improving glycemic control and reducing diabetic distress [6]. Researchers note the different roles of specialist diabetes nurses and primary care nurses in the care of patients with diabetes, emphasizing differences in knowledge and capabilities [7].

DM is a significant burden on the health care system, especially primary care, which is the first point of contact for people seeking health care, and is a key component of the health care system for people with diabetes. This requires nurses to teach patients to self-manage their health and symptoms, according to Dorothea Orem's theory of self-care, as patients cannot be under the constant care of health professionals unless there is a clinical need [8]. The researchers emphasize that this approach requires the use of practical knowledge of nurses to teach patients self-care, taking into account their living conditions and the availability of tools for self-monitoring, such as glucose meters.

As the largest group of medical professionals, nurses are interested in developing and implementing recommendations, guidelines or protocols for the management of a patient with diabetes within the framework of the role of a nurse. A "knowledge-practice gap" has been found to impede holistic integration into daily practice, contributing to high rates of diabetes complications, hospitalizations, and mortality.

Primary care nurses perform not only the role of executors, but also coordinators of the treatment process, teachers and observers of the results of patient treatment. Such versatility emphasizes the adaptability and comprehensive approach of nursing practice in the management of diabetes. Researchers attribute nurses' success to continuous education, improved knowledge, improved dissemination of guidelines and increased awareness, and regular discussions with colleagues to support decisions. Combining active methods (educational meetings and visits) with passive methods (distribution of educational materials) has a greater positive effect on patient adherence than using either method alone [9].

Research data show that nurses who have undergone training in diabetes (training, internship) have better opportunities to provide care and education to patients with diabetes compared to other medical professionals. These are highly qualified nurses who can coordinate, educate, counsel, motivate, manage and assist in the treatment of patients with diabetes; have a significant and positive impact on the education of patients with diabetes [7]. It has been found that, with proper training, nurses can effectively play a role in diabetes care and perform tasks previously performed by physicians. In addition, can develop, implement and provide effective DM interventions through direct care and supervision.

Nurses play an important role in educating and empowering patients for effective self-care, providing the necessary support for people with diabetes, as self-management is a complex process that requires professional involvement. They teach patients self-care techniques that promote risk reduction, problem solving, glucose monitoring, medication administration, physical activity, and healthy eating.

The main goals of diabetes treatment are lifestyle changes and prevention of complications. At the same time, the effectiveness of educational activities depends on how the patient perceives his illness. In addition, socio-demographic factors, such as the level of education, can influence patients' adherence to self-care regimens

during treatment. It has been studied that individual classes are more suitable for some patients, and group classes for others. In addition, nurses are involved in providing a holistic intervention in the treatment of hypertension, hypercholesterolemia and hyperglycemia, which significantly contributes to the reduction of mortality and morbidity in people affected by diabetes.

Nurse practitioners focus on health promotion and disease control by implementing effective strategies such as patient counseling and education [7]. As members of an interdisciplinary team, nurses use a variety of methods to assist patients in self-management. For example, collaboration with dietitians is essential to support healthy food choices and consumption, which is one of the most challenging aspects of diabetes self-management. At the same time, interaction with psychologists helps to advise patients, including people with disabilities, and cooperation with doctors provides the possibility of adjusting treatment plans if necessary.

Nurses also play an important role in patient education and support, especially in insulin administration. Research shows that in some health facilities, the role of nurses has been expanded to include overseeing the prescription and dispensing of medications. The main goal of this model of medical care is to ensure timely access of patients to effective and safe treatment. For example, in New Zealand, registered nurses working in specialist teams and in primary health care are authorized to prescribe certain medications, including antidiabetic drugs, after obtaining appropriate postgraduate training approved by the Nursing Council of New Zealand [10].

Various studies have confirmed the positive results of the role of nurses in improving the management of diabetes. Nurses educate patients about the condition and lifestyle changes they should consider for effective management of the condition, including lifestyle changes and adherence to therapy, and help empower patients through improved glycemic control [10].

Phone consultations are used to support patients with diabetes and teach self-monitoring of blood glucose levels, medications, physical exercises, and diet discussions. Interventions, on the other hand, involve modifying interventions to meet individual preferences, abilities, and needs with nurses to support people in adhering to the proposed treatment plan. The influence of various factors on the effectiveness of DM education and treatment, such as patients' health literacy, self-control and self-efficacy, as well as organizational support and accessibility, has been identified [10].

Nurses can also help patients set personal goals for self-management and problem-solving and change their goals if patients encounter problems, using their own knowledge about diabetes.

Numerous studies emphasize that the presence of psychological problems in patients with diabetes mellitus negatively affects the control and treatment of diabetes and the importance of providing psychological support to patients with diabetes by nurses [7]. In addition, nurses also provide social and emotional support to patients and their family members, which positively affects the results of treatment of patients.

The role of the nurse is important for both patients with diabetes and their family members to develop trust

in the medical staff and for optimal health promotion. They also play an important role in reducing gaps in communication between patients and doctors, playing the role of an intermediate link. Such communication is especially important when diabetes progresses and requires treatment adjustments, such as adding new diabetes medications (eg, insulin) or increasing the dose of medications.

Nurses effectively take responsibility for motivating patients with diabetes. Compared to doctors, they have a better understanding of patients' needs and pay more attention to psychosocial issues that significantly affect disease control and self-care. To do this, nurses use various motivational strategies, including reflection, action support, and teaching to empower patients [7].

Nurses who care for patients with diabetes need practical knowledge and experience to provide quality care. They must have analytical skills (gathering and analyzing information about the patient's condition), communication skills (communicating with patients, other nurses and doctors about changes in health), and interpersonal skills (discussing information with patients and colleagues at a professional level). Also important are leadership skills (managing other nurses and staff), attention to detail (tracking even the smallest changes in glucose levels that can significantly affect the patient's condition), and knowledge (ability to answer questions related to sugar control in blood and other aspects of diabetes).

Nurses must be well-educated in specific issues related to diabetes in order to help patients effectively manage their diabetes. Nurses need to be trained in how to communicate effectively with patients of other cultural backgrounds so that they can offer holistic care.

The researchers propose a three-step model for achieving improved nursing care for patients with diabetes. To achieve the final result, the previous stages must be completed [11]: 1 - training of nurses, availability of appropriate resources and time, as well as cooperation with diabetes specialists; 2 - education of patients with diabetes, provision of extended assistance and motivation of patients with diabetes; 3 - improving nursing care and achieving better results in patients with diabetes.

In addition to appropriate training, changes are needed in the training of nurses and the health care system to expand their role in the treatment, management and prevention of diabetes. Such activities are essential for nurses to fully realize their potential in solving global problems.

Conclusion. Nurses need clearly defined responsibilities and roles in the care of patients with diabetes in the health care system to ensure the best patient care. They also need skills and tools to perform their tasks in different environments. This may include increased use of diagnostic tools, interprofessional patient education, supportive supervision, task sharing, specialized training, and prescribing rights. These roles require recognition in terms of position and qualifications, as well as opportunities for career advancement and pay in-

creases. Increasing the level of interprofessional training could include joint training of nurses at undergraduate and postgraduate levels, which would promote effective teamwork.

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